

AI to Fight Disinformation: a Living Lab Approach

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Abstract

Disinformation is a main problem in today's digital society, as it affects public opinion and causes public harm. This paper introduces research carried out within the Horizon Europe project *anonymised*, where an AI-based engine will be developed to counter disinformation by encouraging citizens' critical thinking processes. The overall implementation methodology of this project consists of a Living Lab approach in three phases. With this, the realization of a socially accepted and trustworthy citizen-centered AI-system will be ensured. This paper will present the findings and results of the first phase within the co-creation process and will cover the expected outcomes of the other two phases.

Key words

Disinformation - Trustworthy AI - Citizen Engagement - User Involvement - Living Labs

Introduction

Today's digital society is characterized by a continuous information flow and can be appointed as the information society (Kobelieva & Nikolaienko, 2021). News and information consumption therefore plays a significant role in citizens' daily practices. Due to this digital transformation, new actors came into play regarding the production, dissemination, and consumption of news. Users took on an active role within those processes and contributed by producing user-generated content (Paulussen et al., 2007). As content production and dissemination was simplified and made accessible to the broad public, the problem of disinformation arose (Rubin, 2019). Disinformation is false information that was spread to intentionally mislead its reader and can harm involved people and institutions (Hernon, 1995).

The aim of this paper is to present the research conducted within the Horizon Europe project *anonymised*. The objective of this project is to develop an AI-based engine that will encourage citizens' critical thinking processes and therefore will aid in fighting disinformation. AI offers opportunities to benefit the social good but equally entails ethical dangers (Hermann, 2021). In addition, using an AI-based system creates its own set of obstacles to overcome in terms of trustworthiness and transparency (Thiebes et al., 2021), these are only amplified by putting it to use in addressing something as controversial in itself as disinformation (Kertysova, 2018).

The application of a citizen-centric approach is required to counter these ethical implications and to ensure the social acceptance and trustworthiness of the AI-based system. The system will therefore be co-created through a process carried out in 3 phases. With this paper we will focus on the question how the application of a Living Lab approach can aid the co-creation of a complex AI-based system. In addition, we will argue how our methodological approach will support both the fighting of disinformation with AI and the assurance of a citizen-centered ecosystem.

Disinformation and the importance of critical thinking

Since the rise of the Internet, numerous ways of disseminating, producing and consuming information arose, resulting in an increasing amount of available online information. Along with this increased availability of information, the necessity to be able to navigate this substantial quantity grew (Hernon, 1995). As the different manners in which one can disseminate and produce information were simplified, the amount of misleading and false

information that was spread increased equally (Fallis, 2015). Besides the simplification of the aforementioned processes, algorithms play a significant role in the creation and spread of disinformation (Kertysova, 2018). One could on the one hand share false information to intentionally mislead and deceive its reader and on the other hand spread misleading information unintentionally, as a genuine mistake. Respectively appointed as *disinformation* and *misinformation* (Hernon, 1995). The disinformation concept will be the focal point within this paper and the project.

The disinformation phenomenon is accompanied by a threat to the values of democratic societies, as it impacts the credibility of institutions, undermines trust, is intended to harm citizens, institutions, or governments (Sadiku et al., 2018) and supports the inception of false beliefs (Fallis, 2015). Critical thinking and the critical assessment of content is crucial to navigate the quantity of online information and limit the consumption of disinformation (Kertysova, 2018). Factors such as relevancy, accessibility, quality (Hernon, 1995), effectiveness, credibility, completeness, depth, authority, belief, and clarity (Rubin, 2019) came into play while critically assessing online information.

The disinformation problem needs to be tackled in order to safeguard the societal values crucial to democracy. The past years, a significant rise in fact-checking tools could be noticed (Akhtar et al., 2022). However, the biggest part of those were dependent on human intervention through the manual screening of online content and tracking down disinformation. Since AI technologies, algorithms, play a part in the production and dissemination of information, the technology gained interest to counter the problem and serve as a solution to disinformation (Kertysova, 2018) through automation (Rubin, 2019).

AI as a solution?

AI technology offers innovative ways to reform, earlier human steered, daily practices and interactions (Hermann, 2021). Since Kaplan and Haenlein (2019) describe AI “*as a system’s ability to interpret external data correctly, to learn from such data, and to use those learnings to achieve specific goals and tasks through flexible adaptation*” (p. 17), it can be applied in a variety of sectors (Akhtar et al., 2022). The technology presents us with different ways to benefit society (Hermann, 2021), and for instance counter disinformation (Akhtar et al., 2022), but equally entails legal and ethical challenges and questions (Kertysova, 2018). With this, the concept of *trustworthy AI* is introduced:

To maximize the benefits of AI while at the same time mitigating or even preventing its risks and dangers, the concept of trustworthy AI (TAI) promotes the idea that individuals, organizations, and societies will only ever be able to achieve the full potential of AI if trust can be established in its development, deployment, and use. (Thiebes et al., 2021, p. 447)

The concept of trust and *trustworthy AI* is crucial within our project’s approach. As the aim is to develop an AI-based system to fight disinformation, social acceptance and trustworthiness are required in order to reach the tools full potential and encourage citizens’ critical thinking processes.

Methodology

The project’s overall implementation methodology is characterized by a citizen-centric co-creation approach to ensure the end product’s trustworthiness, transparency, and acceptance, to increase awareness among the general public (Pierson & Lievens, 2005) and to limit the ethical challenges that are often involved with the application of AI technology (Hermann, 2021). The system will therefore be co-created through a three phase Living Lab process, which will shape its fundamental design principles. The applied methodology offers a new, interesting approach for future Living Labs as the implementation was carried out in different European countries and the different phases lasted, and will last in the future, an entire day. Figure 1 presents an overview of the different phases, its aims and where we currently are in the three phase implementation methodology.

Figure 1. Overview three phase implementation methodology

Phase 1 - Broad European citizen and stakeholder engagement

In the first phase, the emphasis lies on engaging citizens as well as stakeholders to promote trust and acceptance as an integrated feature of the system. By conducting a five-hour co-creation citizen workshop with 30 citizens in 8 European countries, insights were generated on two aspects, namely disinformation and trustworthy AI. The workshops' framework consisted of four sessions. In the first session, the participants were asked to draw a timeline that demonstrated their daily news consumption and equally made them aware of their own habits. During the second session participants had to evaluate ten news articles at first sight, they got 30 seconds to consider each article, and decide whether they were disinformation or true news. This session was able to give an insight into certain triggers that influence the news' credibility evaluation. By touching upon values, habits, and concerns regarding the disinformation problem, these two sessions gave insight into the first aspect.

In the third session participants were offered possible design options during a scenario game, this provided us with the citizens' preferred functionalities and design choices. Features of the system that caused concerns and could result in pitfalls were discussed in the last session through a brainstorm. These last two sessions gave us an understanding of the second aspect: requirements for the successful implementation of a trustworthy AI tool. To further qualify the outcomes and deepen the understanding of the concerns discussed during the citizen workshop, three stakeholder workshops are being conducted.

Phase 2 - The co-creation Lab

In the second co-creation phase, four Living Labs will be conducted across different European countries. These will valorise our research further by implementing an open innovation approach in an early stage of the project. In addition, the Living Labs will provide us with user-feedback on a mock-up of the system (Schuurman et al., 2016). 72 selected citizens will test the AI tool during a five-hour co-creation lab in a real-world setting. The outcomes of this phase will structure a first version of the system.

Phase 3 - Engaging users and uptake of the service - Piloting

In the last phase, both citizens and stakeholders will evaluate and test the first release of the AI-system through three piloting use cases. Each use case will represent a societal challenge and will engage diverse citizen groups. The first use case will target higher

education institutions to ensure a ‘fact-checking state of mind’ among students. The second use case will focus on the involvement of NGOs and provide them with a system to counter disinformation and help them fight against malpractices. The last use case will target citizenship at large and focus on false information regarding migrants and refugees to counter a general negative perception. The pilot results will support the iterative development of the system and will equally show the usage and implementation of the tool into users’ reality. It will demonstrate its performance in a socio-cultural context.

Results phase 1: co-creation citizen workshop

We are currently concluding phase 1 of the research. Subsequently, we are able to report the first findings of the co-creation citizen workshop, carried out as a first part of phase 1. At the OLLD, we will equally be able to present the results of the co-creation stakeholder workshop, to be carried out as a second part of phase 1. There will be no results yet for the later stages of the Living Lab process, phase 2 and 3, as these will be carried out respectively in the end of 2023 and 2024.

The co-creation citizen workshop took place in eight European countries, namely Belgium, Bulgaria, Denmark, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, Slovakia, and Spain. The average participation rate was 27, which made a total of 215 participants who were all purposefully sampled to ensure diversity, as demonstrated in Figure 2. There was however an imbalance in gender, as 61% of the participants were female, 38% was male and 1% indicated *other* as their gender. 27% was between 18 and 29 years old, 21% was 30-39 years old, 18% 40-49 years old, 11% 50-59 years old, 12% 60-69 years old and finally, 11% was above 70 years old.

Figure 2. Gender and age of participants

We can conclude that the critical assessment of online news and information is strongly dependent on the participants' personal knowledge, earlier experiences, and biases. In addition, the provision of personal data appeared to be a threshold for citizens to use the system. As the aim of the system was to offer each user with personalized functionalities to consider individual preferences and needs, this concern complicates the intended personalized design principles.

All concerns mentioned by the participants must be considered and can be divided in four main categories. Firstly, the system must be transparent about the use and storage of personal data. Secondly, the system needs to be adaptable to individual users' needs and requirements. Thirdly, the systems' coaching tool has to be user-friendly and transparent in its functionality. Lastly, to gain trust from citizens, the reasoning and design behind the tool needs to be communicated clearly. These results will be further discussed in detail during the OLLD23 presentation, but the format of this paper did not allow us to give an in-depth explanation here.

Conclusion

The digital society we live in is confronted with the problem of disinformation. Intentionally sharing false information can harm people, public opinion and can cause false beliefs. This forms a threat to democracy and needs to be countered. AI technology

offers the opportunity to aid in this fight against disinformation but equally raises ethical, social, and legal challenges. The goal of the Horizon Europe project *anonymised* is to develop an AI-based system that will encourage citizens' critical thinking and will accordingly contribute to fighting disinformation.

To limit the challenges that AI entails and ensure the development of a socially accepted and trustworthy AI-system, implementing a citizen-centered approach is necessary. The first results of our 3 phase Living Lab approach already demonstrated the complexity of the process. Individual preferences and needs, transparency and trust seem to be crucial elements that will shape the system's fundamental design principles. By continuing this process and iteratively testing and developing the tool with all involved stakeholders from the early stages of the design process, we hope to be able to develop a system that will be used and trusted by citizens in their struggle with the omni-present disinformation problem.

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